

A Novel Architecture with Blockchain-based Identity Management for Industrial Systems

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Abstract—Industrial systems are increasingly interconnected, creating a complex landscape that exposes critical infrastructure to advanced cyber threats. Traditional security measures often fail to address the vulnerabilities in industrial environments where both Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) components must be secured. This paper proposes a novel security architecture that integrates blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) with multi-layered endpoint protection and leverages the principles of the National Institute of Standards and Technology’s (NIST) Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA). By using blockchain-based SSI, the proposed framework provides decentralized and immutable identity verification for all devices, users, and applications and ensures that only authenticated entities can interact within the industrial network. This architecture includes a multi-layered defense model that enables contextual access controls in all layers, from the information systems layers to the control network layer. We evaluate the performance of the architecture, in particular, the latency associated with identity verification and revocation within the critical layers, to show that blockchain-based SSI can enhance security without compromising operational efficiency.

Index Terms—SSI, Blockchain, industrial networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial systems have become increasingly complex and interconnected, driven by advances in automation, digitalization, and the integration of Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) [1]. This convergence has increased operational efficiency while exposing industrial networks to a wide range of security threats. Cyberattacks on Industrial Control Systems (ICSs) can disrupt critical infrastructure, compromise sensitive data, and lead to financial and reputational damage [2]. Traditional security measures designed primarily for isolated systems are often inadequate to protect these interconnected environments from advanced threats. Therefore, there is a growing need for robust, adaptable security solutions that can mitigate risks in dynamic industrial environments [3]. To overcome this challenge, blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) has proven to be a promising solution for improving identity management in industrial systems [4]. By leveraging the decentralized and immutable properties of blockchain, SSI provides a framework that enables secure, traceable, and verified interactions between devices, users, and applications in industrial networks [5]. Unlike traditional identity systems that rely on centralized verification points, SSI allows each entity to manage its

own digital identity and ensure that only authenticated and authorized devices or users interact with the network [6]. This decentralized approach not only strengthens security but also improves privacy and control over identity data, making it an ideal solution for industrial applications where integrity and operational continuity are paramount.

The integration of blockchain technology with SSI frameworks has garnered significant attention in industrial systems, particularly within various domains, such as Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and 6G [7]. Arrizabalaga et al. [8] proposed a Modbus access control system leveraging SSI over Hyperledger Fabric, demonstrating enhanced security and decentralized identity management in industrial communication protocols. Liu et al. [9] introduced design patterns for blockchain-based SSI systems, providing a systematic approach to architecting decentralized identity solutions suitable for various applications, including industrial contexts. Zhang et al. [10] explored a blockchain-based federated learning approach for device failure detection in IIoT, emphasizing data privacy and integrity through decentralized identity verification mechanisms. Cocco and Tonelli [11] discussed the application of blockchain and SSI in the construction sector, emphasizing the role of decentralized identities in enhancing transparency and sustainability. Authors in [12] demonstrated quantum key distribution could be integrated with blockchain based digital identities. These studies collectively highlight the potential of blockchain-based SSI in enhancing security, privacy, and autonomy in industrial systems. However, challenges remain in standardization, interoperability, and scalability, necessitating further research and development in this domain.

In this work, we explore the integration of blockchain-based SSI [13] with multi-layer endpoint protection strategies to improve security at different layers of industrial networks. Furthermore, we discuss the implementation of SSI within the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA) and how this integration can solve the specific security challenges in industrial environments.

Our main contributions are threefold. First, we propose a novel architecture that integrates blockchain-based SSI with a multi-layered endpoint protection model tailored to industrial systems, enabling fine-grained and tamper-proof identity management across both IT and OT domains. Second, we extend the NIST Zero Trust Architecture by embedding SSI-

based authentication and revocation logic into the control and data planes, thereby strengthening access enforcement and auditability in critical infrastructure environments. Third, we implement and evaluate a latency-optimized SSI deployment using Hyperledger Fabric and REST APIs under realistic multi-threaded, Poisson-distributed workloads, demonstrating lower verification and revocation latency compared to conventional cloud-based SSI approaches.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Layers of Defence

Layers of Defence in [14] can be integrated with SSI, where a multi-layered approach to cyber security with different layers of security is depicted, each designed to protect against different types of threats and vulnerabilities. Each layer in this model deals with different aspects of security, starting with the innermost layer, the device layer. This layer focuses on securing physical devices such as computers, mobile devices, and IoT devices through methods such as device hardening, patch management, and endpoint protection to prevent unauthorized access and malware infections. The application layer ensures the security of software applications by using secure coding practices, application firewalls, and regular security assessments to protect against vulnerabilities and attacks. The computer layer focuses on securing the operating systems and computing environments on which applications are executed. It uses access controls, antivirus solutions, and system monitoring to detect and mitigate threats at the operating system level.

The network layer secures the communication channels between devices and systems through the use of firewalls, intrusion detection/prevention systems (IDPS) and encryption to protect data in transit and prevent unauthorized network access. The physical layer addresses the security of the physical environment in which the devices and systems are housed and implements measures such as secure server rooms, surveillance systems and access controls to prevent physical tampering or theft. At the outermost level, policies, procedures & awareness represent organizational efforts to promote a culture of safety. These include user training, incident response plans and compliance with regulatory standards to ensure that security measures are understood and adhered to throughout the organization. To further improve this defense in depth model, a new layer can be introduced: Blockchain-based SSI. This SSI layer sits between the application and compute layers and would focus on securing identity management across systems and applications. By leveraging the decentralized and immutable nature of blockchain, this layer would ensure that all identities within the network, whether of users, devices or services are verified and authenticated. This would add a robust layer of protection that prevents unauthorized access and ensures that all interactions within the network are traceable and verifiable. The SSI layer would work closely with both the network and application layers, providing secure identity verification for communication and access to applications. By integrating SSI into the Defense in

Depth strategy, organizations can significantly improve their security posture and reduce the risk of identity theft, insider threats and unauthorized access [15]. This additional layer of identity management complements existing layers of security and creates a more resilient and comprehensive defense against a variety of cyber threats.

B. Different Threats

Various threats and vulnerabilities in industrial environments could be exploited by external threat actors [16]. Fig. 1 gives a summary of potential threats and vulnerabilities in industrial environments. At the top are external threat actors, which could include hackers or other malicious entities attempting to penetrate the industrial system. These threat actors attempt to penetrate the network by exploiting vulnerabilities such as weak password policies on servers and weak separation between endpoints and other systems, even if they are protected by firewalls. As we move deeper into the industrial environment, the diagram shows further risks in the IT/OT convergence layer, such as outdated software on systems like control room workstations. These outdated systems often lack the latest security patches, making them a prime target for attacks. Written copies of passwords on technical workstations further exacerbate security risks, as sensitive credentials are vulnerable to theft or misuse. The diagram also shows the lack of segmentation in network design, which allows an attacker to move laterally across systems and compromise various devices such as Human-Machine Interfaces (HMIs), Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs), and other critical infrastructure components.

Fig. 1: Different threats in industrial environments.

Another significant risk is the presence of forgotten devices on the network, such as older PLCs, which may no longer be actively managed or monitored. If left unprotected, these devices could serve as a gateway for attackers to gain unauthorized access to the industrial control system [17]. To mitigate these vulnerabilities, integrating blockchain-based

SSI into the industrial environment can provide a robust solution. Blockchain-based SSI ensures that all entities within the network, whether users, devices, or software applications, are authenticated through a decentralized and immutable identity verification process. By implementing SSI, organizations can enforce strong, cryptographically secured password policies, eliminate the need for written passwords through passwordless authentication, and ensure that only verified and authorized devices and users can interact with critical systems [18]. In addition, blockchain-based SSI can improve network segmentation by providing identity-based access controls that prevent unauthorized lateral movement within the network. This would also make forgotten devices and outdated software less of a security threat, as these systems would require valid, up-to-date credentials for each operation within the network. In summary, the integration of blockchain-based SSI into this industrial environment would significantly reduce the risk of these presented threats and create a more secure and resilient infrastructure against external threats [7].

III. MULTI-LAYERED ENDPOINT PROTECTION WITH SSI

A multi-layered endpoint protection architecture in an industrial environment is given in Figure 2. This figure illustrates the various networks and systems involved in maintaining security in the OT and IT infrastructures of a factory. It is a comprehensive, multi-layered endpoint protection system that integrates both the information systems network and the control information network in a factory environment.

The information system network with PCs and servers is in an office environment. Blockchain-based SSI can be implemented here to manage the identities of all devices and users within this network. Each device and user would have a unique, cryptographically secure identity, ensuring that only authorized individuals and systems can access sensitive data and applications. This would prevent unauthorized access and ensure that all interactions within this network are verifiable and secure. The middle area shows the Control Information Network, which establishes a connection to important systems such as the Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and the database Open Platform Communications (OPC) server. These systems are essential for managing production processes and the flow of data within the factory. In this network, a blockchain-based SSI would ensure that all data exchanges and system interactions are carried out by authenticated entities. For example, the MES and OPC servers would only accept data from sources with verified SSI credentials to prevent unauthorized or malicious data entry. In addition, the IDS (Intrusion Detection System) would be extended with SSI functions so that it could not only detect anomalies but also verify the identity of all devices and users involved in the communication.

The Control Information Network shows the connection to various control systems such as MES, ES (Engineering Station), DCS (Distributed Control System), and PLC (Programmable Logic Controllers), as well as field bus systems

for controlling robot arms. In the control network, blockchain-based SSI would be crucial to ensure that only verified devices and systems can communicate with each other. For example, DCS and PLC would verify the identities of MES and ES before executing commands or processing data. This level of authentication would significantly reduce the risk of unauthorized access or cyber-attacks and ensure the integrity of control processes. The field bus connects various robot systems within the factory, which are crucial for automated production processes. Each robotic system would be assigned an SSI to ensure that only authorized commands from authenticated devices are executed. This prevents unauthorized interventions that could interrupt the production line or cause safety risks.

Figure 2 also illustrates the possibilities of remote maintenance and local maintenance, where technicians can use external devices (e.g. USB drives) to interact with the network. Blockchain-based SSI would verify the identities of both maintenance personnel and their devices before allowing interaction with the network. This ensures that only trusted individuals with verified identities can perform maintenance tasks, reducing the risk of malware or unauthorized changes being introduced into the system. Connections to external factories and the internet are displayed, which are protected by firewalls. Blockchain-based SSI would be used to manage and verify identities across these external connections. Any data or communications passing through the firewall would require SSI authentication to ensure that only legitimate traffic can interact with the internal networks. Overall, the integration of blockchain-based SSI into this multi-layered endpoint protection system enhances security by ensuring that all devices, users and systems within the network are authenticated and authorized, significantly reducing the risk of cyber threats and unauthorized access.

IV. ZERO TRUST ARCHITECTURE WITH SSI

NIST provides the ZTA framework in [19]. Fig. 3 represents an extended version of the ZTA framework and is now divided into three main planes: the control plane, the data plane, and blockchain-based SSI. The framework emphasizes that no entity, whether inside or outside the network, is trusted by default. Instead, trust is continuously evaluated through a policy-based approach. *In the control plane:* The Policy Decision Point consists of a Policy Engine and a Policy Administrator. This is where access control decisions are made on the basis of predefined policies. Blockchain-based SSI can be integrated here to improve the decision-making process. The policy engine would verify the SSI credentials of the subject (user or system) requesting access and ensure that only entities with valid, cryptographically secure identities are considered for access approval. This process includes verifying the immutable records associated with each SSI to confirm the authenticity and validity of the subject's identity. The Control Plane receives input from various sources, such as the CDM (Continuous Diagnostics and Mitigation) system, industry compliance, threat intelligence, and Activity logs. Each of these inputs can be improved by integrating SSI. For example,

Fig. 2: Multi-layered endpoint protection with SSI.

activity logs could include SSI-based authentication records that provide a tamper-proof history of all access attempts and policy decision point decisions. Similarly, compliance and threat intelligence data could be linked to verified SSI credentials to ensure that all inputs to the decision-making process come from trusted, authenticated sources.

by the Policy Decision Point. It separates untrusted systems from trusted industry resources. The Policy Enforcement Point can leverage blockchain-based SSI to enforce access decisions. The PEP verifies the SSI credentials provided by the subject against the guidelines defined in the Control Plane. Only after successful verification of these credentials does the PEP allow the system to access the trusted industry resources. On the right side of the data plane, the industry resource is what the subject is trying to access, e.g. data, applications or services. Access to these resources is further secured by ensuring that only subjects with verified SSI identities that have passed the Policy Enforcement Point can access them. The resources themselves may also have SSI-based protections in place to ensure that every interaction with them is fully authenticated and logged.

Fig. 3: Multi-layered endpoint protection with SSI.

In the data plane: On the left side of the data plane, the subject (a user or device) interacts with a system that is trying to access an enterprise resource. Before the system can even contact the Policy Enforcement Point, the individual’s SSI credentials are verified. This ensures that only subjects with valid SSI identities that have been recognized and verified by the control plane can continue the process. This step significantly reduces the risk of untrusted or malicious entities attempting to access industry resources. The Policy Enforcement Point acts as a gatekeeper that enforces the access control decisions made

Various supporting systems are also included that interact with the Control Plane: Data Access Policy, Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), ID management, Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) System. Blockchain-based SSIs can be integrated into these systems to improve security and identity management. For example: Policies can be defined for data access policies that require SSI authentication for access to specific data. For PKI, SSI could work alongside PKI and provide a decentralized and immutable identity verification system. For ID management, SSI becomes a core part of ID management and ensures that all identities within the system are verifiable and secure. For SIEM systems, SSI can enrich the SIEM system with authenticated logs and alerts and ensure that all security events can be traced back to verified identities.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Identity verification and identity revocation are time-critical functions in the lifecycle of industrial automation services. Identity verification requires a real-time response to eliminate latency trade-off against security functions. This experiment evaluates the benefits of integrating blockchain for SSI in

industrial automation architecture in multi-scaled environments. In this experiment, we implemented a near-realistic environment for the proposed use case using the decentralized computing infrastructure of the proposed architecture with four virtual machines and one host machine. The virtual machines run Ubuntu 18.10 64-bit with 4 GB RAM and a single core allocation. The host machine has an Intel(R) Core i5 - 8250 CPU with four cores and eight logical processors. The Hyperledger Fabric blockchain is deployed on each virtual machine with REST Application Programming Interface (API) connectivity to simulate the SSI service in the proposed architecture. The API integration provides flexibility and seamless interoperability as required in the realistic scenarios. We initialized the system with pre-registered entities to simulate the authentication scenarios of a production-grade behavior.

Fig. 4: SSI implementation setup.

The implementation evaluates latency, an important performance parameter for industrial settings operating with dynamic authentication. To simulate a more realistic scenario, we implemented our experiment with multi-threaded software programs to launch the authentication requests of devices and users following a Poisson arrival with different mean values. This simulates the arrival of requests at different transaction rates with the variable λ . Transaction generation follows a Poisson distribution with the rate parameter λ and the probability of observing k events in the time period, denoted as

$$P(X = k) = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^k}{k!} \quad (1)$$

The average of the measuring parameter R for N requests triggered on each λ is denoted as

$$\bar{R} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N R_i \quad (2)$$

A. Identity verification latency using SSI blockchain layer

In this experiment, we evaluated the latency of the identification verification of the simulated SSI blockchain layer. In particular, the SSI blockchain layer enables the authorization of devices and users in real time and with lower latency to ensure the efficient functioning of the application workflow. Our work leverages blockchain-based smart contracts to run SSI as a decentralized service that enables the portability of services at the edge infrastructure layer. In this experiment, we increased the λ value according to the (1) and evaluated the batch completion latency. As can be seen in Figure 5, our work results in lower latency than the cloud-based SSI approach. The results show that our work reflects the significant advantage of decentralizing services from the cloud to the edge.

Fig. 5: Elapsed verification time compared to the increasing average transactions per second.

B. Identity revocation latency of the SSI blockchain layer

In our work, the devices and users are connected with the digital identity. As much as identity generation and verification in real-time, identity revocation also plays a vital role in the SSI lifecycle. Especially when a particular device or user is being off-boarded from the system, the SSI has to be revoked. The reasons for potential off-boarding include the end of serving life of users and devices as well as potential security threats identified by the IDS. In this experiment, we simulated a dynamic SSI revocation scenario with the blockchain-integrated SSI. From the results shown in Figure 6, our work shows lower latency compared to the cloud-based state-of-the-art system. Our work removes the potential bottleneck that may occur in cloud-based SSI systems with improved security by including the revocation record in the distributed ledger for cryptographic integrity preservation.

C. Insights from the results and discussion

The experimental results demonstrate that our work is well-applicable for for a production-grade deployment by design that envisions for reduced latency on identity verification and revocations. The API-based integration points especially ensure flexibility for seamless integration with existing systems with the decentralized operation of smart contracts. The smart

Fig. 6: Elapsed revocation time compared to the increasing average transactions per second.

contract-based operation of the APIs and associated functions guarantee the service integrity, while achieving efficiency in request processing with reduced latency. The experimental results clearly reflect the improvement of identity verification latency and certificate revocation latency beyond state of the art. The results clearly reflect the significant benefits of the proposed architecture for industry automation use cases. In addition, the consensus-driven transaction processing eliminates the risk of the services at cloud are maliciously being modified.

In future evaluations, we aim to include additional performance indicators such as CPU and memory overhead of the blockchain nodes, transaction throughput under varying request densities, and qualitative security assessments under simulated adversarial scenarios. These metrics will provide a more comprehensive view of the practicality and robustness of the proposed architecture in large-scale deployments.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a novel architecture that combines blockchain-based SSI with multi-layered endpoint protection to enhance identity and trust in industrial systems. By extending the NIST ZTA with decentralized identity verification and revocation mechanisms, the solution supports fine-grained, secure access control across IT and OT domains. Latency evaluations confirm that the proposed approach outperforms traditional cloud-based SSI models in critical authentication paths, enabling real-time protection in industrial settings.

Nonetheless, several challenges remain. These include scalability under high-concurrency scenarios, protection of sensitive identity metadata, and integration with legacy equipment or compliance constraints. Future work will address these aspects and expand the system to federated environments across other industrial sectors. Furthermore, post-quantum capabilities will also be considered for such systems [20].

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